

THE MUSICAL PHENOMENON SEPULTURA: HOW THE GRUPO MINEIRO CHANGED THE INTERNATIONAL TRASH METAL SCENE

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the theme of the trash metal band from Minas Gerais, Sepultura and how their incomparable sound and styles changed the international metal scene. Formed in 1984, in the city of Belo Horizonte, they won over fans all over the world thanks to a sui generis musical production, packed with heavy guitar riffs, never-before-seen drums and sinister vocals. This is a work that explores the genius of the group and their music, analyzing what they created that was new and that cannot be reproduced by anyone else. It is configured as a bibliographical research, based on years of studies and monitoring of the Caras' work. The group's entire musical development permeates the sound evolution they have experienced over decades, allowing them to enjoy creative freedom in the style that makes them living legends. Sepultura is not considered the greatest ultra-heavy rock group in the history of music, because in its home country it is not recognized as such. Sepultura is Brazilian; but, it's not from Brazil! It does not represent the type of recognition that a group of fops and half-assed critics want for the Brazilian music scene. Even with all the merit achieved through their personal efforts, they are not seen as the greatest Brazilian musical star.

Keywords: Severe; Trash Metal; International musical phenomenon.

INTRODUCTION

The heavy rock group, Sepultura, originating from the mining city of Belo Horizonte (Brazil), can be considered, without any special appreciation, as being the only *trash metal band* to emerge on the international *Heavy Metal scene*. No other musical band managed to unite *punk*, with its unique and noisy sound, with the speed and weight of hard metal and, to complete a *sui generis condition*, Max Cavalera's vocals combined perfectly with the drum sound of his brother, Igor. Cavalera, one of the most iconic musicians in history; so unique that no one has ever tried to copy his playing; simply because it is impossible to achieve such a feat.

Sepultura was born amidst the effervescence of *trash metal*, a musical style whose precursor was the American band Metallica and their debut album *Kill 'Em All* (1983), alongside another band, also with a powerful style of sound, Slayer. There were other groups that expressed very heavy music and unique styles, such as Kronos, from Norway; However, the production that the band from Minas Gerais put into their *riffs*, especially after the arrival of Andreas Kisser, made them a *trash legend*, destined to do so since the release of the album *Beneath the Remains* (1989), which mixes punk rock progressive and ultra aggressive by Ratos de Porão and a classical guitar, with notes defined by the hands of a unique musician. This album was considered by *Terrorizer magazine* as one of the 20 best *thrash metal albums* of all time.

The band did not become, in the opinion of the media and critics, the greatest *trash metal band* in history for two very simple reasons, the first being that it was never the dream of the Cavalera brothers, *glamor* above their art, as Max would later declare this on several occasions. The second issue, and no less important, is that the investment in *marketing* on the guys' work was not enough to face bands with greater commercial prestige in the music market.

There is a third factor, which is very complex to analyze, which is the issue of sound. Even after signing a contract with the North American record label Roadrunner, Sepulturas did not sell themselves to the music market and their sound, although it received due sound polish, remained rough and aggressive as always and Max's vocals proved that they didn't care about the critics. of art and what they really wanted was to play their music, in the way they believed to be the best way to express it.

Wagner Lamounier, former vocalist of the band and leader of the Minas Gerais *death metal group* Sarcópagó, stated about the polishing of Sepultura's sound that the guitar bases and double bass were recorded by Andreas Kisser, in open criticism of the phenomenon that proved to be the production of the albums *Beneath te remains* (1989) and *Arise* (1991). They were never called *trash traitors*, which already guarantees that the guys have style and determination in what they do.

With the release of the album *Arise*, in 1991, the band became so relevant in the North American and international metal scene that comic strips even appeared *in the* ⁴United States, in which the members of the rock group Metallica and Slayer appeared, together with the Hollywood actor Arnold Schwarzenegger, represented in the figure of his iconic *Terminator* chasing the components of Sepultura, hunting them, to kill (obviously). The message is very

⁴ Comic strips are a textual genre characterized by short stories, generally made up of three or four comics. Usually using humor, strips can only tell a story; but sometimes they have additional purposes, such as social criticism.

clear, the bands mentioned feared the success that the group from Minas Gerais was destined for. Unfortunately, this piece was very little disseminated in the Brazilian music scene and what we saw, in fact, was countless criticisms, motivated by envy of what they achieved, with serious and professional work.

Rock n' roll has always had an overtly political bias; this has been present since the Beatles and John Lennon, with their syrupy *Imagine*, through Black Sabbath, with their *Children of the Grave*; Slayer, with their *War ensable*, Metallica, with *Disposable Heroes* and, not counting international punk rock, but which stands out, without any space for discussion, the Brazilian group from São Paulo, Ratos de Porão, Sepultura's classic musical influence. Thus, the lyrics of the group Sepultura have always presented strong criticism of politics and the System as a whole. They were not talking about any specific country or nation; their target is the policies and directions that governments give them, and this stance was never well received by the media, which, given its hermeneutic-linguistic delay, took what the Guys wrote as personal offenses to Brazil and Brazilians.

Brazil has excellent musical quality, with good artists and very strong lyrics; However, most of the time, artists confuse their lives in the art world with personal confrontations with the system and this causes them to be seen as subversive figures who should be avoided, including their music, which makes the State and record companies do not invest in international dissemination of works to the extent that this is necessary to impose Brazilian music in the world.

Sepultura, from their coexistence with North American *punk culture* and their Ratos de Porão heritage, learned to treat politics as their main target, without carrying out direct attacks on individuals, that is, they did not personalize it. Only with great effort were [*supposed*] Brazilian journalists able to interpret their lyrics as direct attacks on Brazilian democracy, while the troublemakers who remained here fought against oppression; therefore, it wasn't fair that Sepulturas, from Minas Gerais [*and not Rio de Janeiro*] were loved and idolized around the world [*and also in Brazil*], promoting Brazilian musical culture, singing in a language they were not from. native speakers.

In December 1996, what no one expected happened: Max Cavallera announced his departure from the group, abandoning his brother Igor and his companions from difficult days. At this moment, the band's future becomes uncertain, especially because although the music they played had become iconic due to the set of instruments and voice, everyone knows, declaredly, that Max's vocals, combined with Igor's drums represent the musical spirit of the group.

As is only natural in the 21st century, the band survived; but, the Sepultura on which this essay focuses is the one formed by Max Cavalera (Vocals and guitar), Igor Cavalera (Drums), Andreas Kisser (Guitar) and Paulo Júnior (Bass). Not that the formations that followed this one don't characterize the group's musical style; just that, building a career from nothing in the world of music is a feat that cannot be ignored and, even if there may be future dissent from fans, a fan never stops being a fan, enjoying something that the your favorite band produced it at some point. Human memory is linked to very particular feelings that mark existence and, to be very clear, it is strange that, even without the Cavalera brothers, the group survived. This shows that Sepultura has become much bigger than any of them, just as Max's desire and dream has always been and because he fought throughout his life at the head of the group. Paradoxically, his departure is due to the fact that, at a certain point, he ended up seduced by the idea that the greatness that the name Sepultura had achieved was thanks to him, putting himself above the hard work carried out by all the members of the group.

THE ICONIC AND UNIQUE STYLE OF IGOR CAVALERA

In rock n' roll, the drums are extremely important to support the strident and low sound of the guitar, a unique mark of the style and, when you listen to the beat, you can see that it has a cadence and a sequence capable of imposing strength and vibration to the sound produced. In the case of the *trash metal style*, this requirement becomes stronger, with beat shapes that highlight the aggressive sound, which means that the interval between each beat is reduced, in other words, a faster and more powerful drum.

Even with all this demand regarding the sound beat of the drums and their accessories, there is a cadence that can be followed, a situation that does not happen with the style of Igor Cavalera, Sepultura's original drummer, in which the sound produced by his instrument seems obey your desire and not just your knocks. This way of playing the aforementioned instrument makes him an unparalleled and incomparable drummer, and we can say that it is impossible to copy and reproduce his way of playing, which made Sepultura have a unique, brutal and, at the same time, sonically polished sound, which can be understood as a paradox, because the entire explanation presented so far shows something surreal in the world of heavy music.

Igor Cavalera is a phenomenon in his own right; its musical evolution from the albums in which the group expressed itself with a *Death Metal sound* until reaching the *trash style* is impressive, in which it adds speed, rhythm and an incredible sound polish, so well worked that, in a show, if, by chance, If he dedicated himself to an endless solo, the audience would continue

to applaud him and go wild with every beat. His ability as a percussionist led the American *hardcore band* Guns N' Roses to invite him to join the sextet when Matt Sorum left. It's not surprising that Guns invited him, despite him being an ultra-heavy rock drummer and the band in question working in a more *hard rock/hardcore line*, with some ballads, including the insertion of classical music instruments. The fact is that, in the world of music, few drummers were privileged with public recognition for their performances, and what the Brazilian musician accomplished is something unprecedented in the international history of heavy rock, in which he evolved from his own style, merging the *punk mode*, à la Ratos de Porão, with a strong, heavy beat and in a sequence that is difficult to believe could be performed by a human being.

It would be interesting to think what he could add to the sound of Guns N' Roses, alongside an epic guitarist passionate about Blues, like Slash and a bassist who knows international *punk rock* like no other, like Duff McKagan. Speculations aside, I believe that Igor could add weight and speed to Guns' sound and they could create new songs in the style of *Appetite For Destruction* (1987), improved and more aggressive in the beats and strings.

Even if it is remotely admitted that Igor Cavalera has received influences from other styles and musicians, the fact is that his way of playing the drums is so unique that you don't see other musicians trying to imitate him or take him as an influence. In a previous interview, from 2022, Max, his brother and road companion, highlighted that Igor does not receive due credit for his musical ability. “Igor never learned music; never had a drum lesson; That's why the things he created on those records are impressive to this day. There are drummers who study what Igor did and can't understand it. He is a very creative drummer. Every move he makes, (...) he is very creative. I think he doesn't get the credit... he should get more credit in the world of world drummers, because he's so creative. More than the technical aspect, it is the creation, which I think is more difficult than the technique” (MAX, 2002/2024, sp).

This statement by Max already allows us to deduce that musical critics tended to say that Igor Cavalera does not have the technique to play the drums and, the boy's silence, in this sense, already gives us an idea of his response to these individuals: he *does not play the drums nor He makes music to please critics and to delight his fans*. It turns out that his style does not allow him to rhythmically follow a logical cadence of the instrument, as other heavy rock percussionists do, which does not mean, under any circumstances, that he does not have a technique; It's just not what scholars want to hear, much less what they consider ideal. The fact is that, a study method would have to be created in order to analyze and interpret Igor's musical style, and the Brazilian public university could well do it and, if it doesn't, the reason is quite

simple: most of Brazilian musicians hate Sepultura and critics try to ignore what the Guys created and what they represent for the history of international music, as a whole and not just in the *trash/death metal style* .

Every now and then a reporter from a newspaper appears trying to reconcile Sepultura with the Brazilian music scene, as if they could be compared to any Brazilian band besides Ratos de Porão and they also try to claim that they were responsible for taking Brazil's name for the foreign music market. It's pushing the envelope too much when defending such an idea, because the only thing the Cavalera Brothers actually did was publicize the unrecognized work of their band here in Brazil, which was promptly recognized in Europe and the United States of America. . With this, I don't mean to say that there wasn't hard work in production and innovation in the musical style; but, who achieved fame and merit for their efforts, influencing other big names in Metal, even generating envy in international music monsters.

Unfortunately, the propaganda about Sepultura and their work was distorted, starting with the fact that they did not sing in Portuguese and numerous cartoons were published in national magazines distorting their lyrics, as if they were criticizing Brazil, in a pejorative way. Therefore, claiming that a drummer has no technique and, based on this simple excuse, ignoring all of their creativity and style is a case with no other explanation than the attempt to hide the envy of the success they have achieved as musicians and as a band.

MAX CAVALERA'S ICONIC AND UNIQUE VOCALS

Max Cavalera, the lead singer of Sepultura until December 1996, was not the one who originally took over the vocals in his band. Another former member, Wagner Lamounier, was in charge of imposing a voice on the group's initial style, *Death Metal* , which would later be transmuted into trash, with his departure and in his place, his brother Cavalera assuming responsibility. of being the singer, while continuing to act as the rhythm guitarist.

Max Cavalera's voice is known worldwide for being strong and guttural, being an influence on many other musicians. The difference in vocal style between him and Wagner is that the former had a very heavy style, focused on death, in which Sepultura was a pioneer in the world and Max's vocal timbre did not accompany this sound and, there was the issue that the punk rock influences on the band would lead it to the *trash metal style* , in which Max's vocals fit perfectly, creating a musical ensemble formed by Kisser's guitar, Igor's drums and lyrics directly addressing current political issues. .

Sepultura's transition from the *Death Metal style*, with guttural vocal sounds, to the *Trash Metal style*, with more serious and heavy sounds, is largely due to Max's vocals and not to a change in ideology regarding his beliefs. There is one detail, in which the Minas Gerais music scene has more to do with Black Metal and, as strange as such a statement may seem, Sepultura has much more of a São Paulo musical profile, with a powerful influence from Punk Rock, especially Ratos. de Porão, who were, in Brazil, the precursors of the most authentic international *Trash Metal*.

João Gordo, lead singer of Ratos, may have been Max Cavalera's greatest vocal influence and this was the biggest insight they had regarding the direction the band would take from their classic albums *Beneath the remains* (1989) and *Arise* (1991), recorded by the American Roadrunner Records, which saw greater potential for impact on the music market for the band, with Max adapting his vocals to this specific style.

Max's vocals are iconic and unique, producing bass with great precision and, on certain occasions, comparisons with the issue of linguistic expression appeared, in which an attempt was made to compare the native English of James Hetfield (lead singer of Metallica) with the guttural English of the Brazilian and, given the proportions, the situation analyzed today is ridiculous, because they are completely different styles of musical production, in which Metallica persisted in *heavy metal* with a little more speed, staying between this style and trash, while Sepultura created a style that lies between *Trash* and *Death Metal*; therefore, classifying them as having their music belonging to the *Trash style* is arbitrary and absurd, functioning more as a condition of rhetoric, with the purpose of better understanding and discussing its relevance in the international musical scene.

One very interesting thing about Max's vocals is that, as he got older, his voice became more powerful, more intense, which provides a unique style to *Trash Metal*, a situation that places him as an icon of the style, recognizing him as a living rock legend for many years. His way of singing, in which he makes short forays into his choruses, in a punk rock style, allows him to achieve a peculiar sound with an emblematic style.

It could even be that he took singing lessons; perhaps, to improve some characteristic of your voice; but, when he is on stage, his *performance* is so unique that one can even doubt that this ever happened. Max revealed, in an interview, in 2022, that he *never* took formal music lessons, perhaps singing; which can be understood by its unique characteristic and linearity in maintaining its musical determinations.

The lyrics of Sepultura's songs are written in short choruses that allow Max to add additional weight and create the necessary interval to charge his lungs with oxygen and give

the trash/Black tone that brings out the sound of a voice filled with a singularity never before seen in music. His transposition from *Death Metal* to *Trash Metal* was a true musical evolution and, not just a vocal development, from the maturation of the adolescent voice to an adult voice, which is characterized as an extraordinary phenomenon that, perhaps, not even Max himself has realized how this happened and how this arouses interest and curiosity in other musicians and some music scholars and also, if I dare say, in doctors specializing in otorhinolaryngology and speech therapy.

Although it is not the best option to define the success of a band based on a single member, because the end result is the expression of teamwork, one cannot disregard how much the songs and lyrics of the band Sepultura suit Max's vocals; considering that this adjustment of the lyrics, the meter of the poem, the size of the chorus, the meaning itself, imposing a singular meaning on it, is not just any work that happens as if by miracle or by chance. As he rightly states, that he does not have an instructor to assist him in this construction, relying only on his music producer to adjust everything in the studio, this proves, once again, his immeasurable genius and musical creativity.

THE INFLUENCE OF PUNK ROCK AND THE CLASSICAL TRAINING WITH ANDREAS KISSER GAVE SEPULTURA AN INCOMPARABLE MUSICAL STYLE

The influence of heavy punk rock on Sepultura's production and musical style is indelible and can be seen in the lyrics, sound, drums and vocals, meaning the four band members managed to create a unique, heavy *Trash Metal style*. , fast, short songs, poems dealing with sociopolitical issues with a lot of acidity and violence. This mix was possible thanks to the band's contact with the São Paulo music scene, where individuals are more indifferent to what is expressed and, to complete the central element in all of this, the presence of Andreas Kisser as the group's main guitarist and the entire his classical formation which, combined with the heavy feeling of overcoming the Minas Gerais people, gave rise to a guitar style that would become emblematic, iconic.

Andreas studied classical music, as well as guitar and instrumental techniques; he knew the backstage of the organization between the musical elements and their influences when united in the same group of tones and sounds. Interesting that, at first, it suits Sepultura's *death style*; However, the sound evolves, creating the basis for Max's vocals to adapt to a timbre that would sound emblematic in the world of ultra-heavy rock. At the same time, he contributed to Igor's drumming and his *performance* developing in such a way that it became unmistakable. It

may seem like a joke, but it is Kisser's guitar that provides the musical foundations for Igor to create a *sui generis* sound with his drums, without this detracting from him as a musician and, quite the opposite; This condition makes him the most phenomenal guitarist in the entire history of *Trash Metal*, acting as an authentic maestro on stage and on studio albums.

The musical quality that Sepultura achieved from the albums *Beneath the reamins* (1989) and *Arise* (1991) is due to Kisser's guitar, which managed to polish the sound of the other base instruments to the point that, Wagner Lamounier, in an interview with At the time of the release of the last album mentioned, it was said that Andreas played all the string instruments during the recording. It's evil of you to make such a statement, even because led by a great maestro and a great master of music, the other components feel motivated to improve their styles and technical-professional development in what they already did and found themselves limited, perhaps due to lack of direct contact with someone who is excellent at what they do, simply because they are excellent *par excellence* ! This is the case of Andreas Kisser. In August 2012, he received his own brick on the *Cavern Club* 's wall of fame ⁵. He became the first Brazilian to have one, and the first modern metal guitarist to be honored in this way.

The freedom of production and expression that Sepultura always experienced, as a heavy rock band, to create their own musical arrangements made them a phenomenological sumptuousness in the world of music and, individually, each of the members grew in creativity until they became giants. and, at the same time, incomprehensible as musicians, where their creations cannot simply be reproduced, which, on the one hand, is fantastic, because it makes it unique and is, at the same time, something very complex, given in a world where the creative capacity is at a low ebb and the majority are thirsty for some kind of musical substitute. The only alternative is to listen to the original and try to understand it and, if you can't do so, continue listening to it anyway.

It's no surprise when kisser revealed that Steve Vai couldn't reproduce Sepultura's music and this is equivalent to saying that no other living guitarist can, because Vai is a living legend and a guy capable of deciphering songs that are almost impossible to do. It turns out that what the band's musicians created and still create is something surreal for the stereotypical models of musical art that plague the current scenario.

Andreas became the musical phenomenon that he is by being in Sepultura. This statement may seem bizarre; However, a series of situations leads us to interpret this occurrence as something that, if he had been in another band, he would not have been able to be recognized

⁵ *Cavern Club* is an English themed bar specializing in musical performances, located in the city of Liverpool. It became known worldwide for being the starting point of the Beatles' career.

as the creative musician he has become over the years. He is the only one in the band's original formation who had studied music formally and, when he joined the group, instead of imposing the canonical ideas he had learned, he took advantage of all the freedom that the other members had, as they were not graduates of musical schools. and, thus, he does what he always wanted to do in terms of sound and musicality; he was the one who adapted to the style of autonomous musicians, the extremely raw sound of Igor's drums and Max's heavy and sonorous vocals, and the result was a brutal sound coming from his guitar and, at the same time, melodious, well crafted; a mix that the metal world has seen on very few occasions.

CONCLUSION

The *Trash Metal band Sepultura* from Minas Gerais is the most perfect consolidation of the style, not being surpassed by any other and, despite going through complex situations, such as the departure of the Cavalera brothers, Igor and Max, it persisted as a personification of international Trash, which reveals that his fan base was built on his music and his independent, autonomous, incomparable musical style. Since gaining its classical training, it has emerged in the heavy rock music scene as a group with the potential to make a difference in the music scene.

With the addition of Andreas Kisser in 1986, the group experienced a true technical and musical evolution, with Max's vocals adjusting to Igor's guitar and drums until reaching the *Trash Metal style*, abandoning *Death Metal*, the initial style they adopted. . From then on, the influence of Ratos de Porão became clear, both in sound and lyrics. International recognition arrived and, along with it, the opportunity to record with a North American producer, which launched a promising career that continues to this day.

Unfortunately, in 1996, Max left the band he had created in 1984, together with his brother Igor, and even if one does not want to say that a single member of a group is what sustains all its *glamour*, it cannot be denied. that sepultura's vocals and lyrics were created to be performed by Max Cavalera and no one else. It's a strange chapter in the band's history; But what can be understood is that Max belongs to a time when leaving a band and then forming another was the most normal thing in the world of rock; However, times have changed and, if there is still resentment on the part of the vocalist against his former companions, it was not because he left or for other reasons; It was precisely because they allowed him to leave. Not that he's the type who likes to be flattered; but, they were friends from the band's *dark days*; There was there [*or at least he believed there was*] a type of feeling that would never accept a

dissolution that was not determined by the end of existence itself. This is the kind of wound that never heals; because it is understood as a betrayal, an emotional abandonment.

Ten years later, drummer Igor Cavalera also left the band. What one might think would end without the Cavalera brothers proved to be a mistaken idea and the permanence of the group Sepultura on the international music scene, producing great records is proof that it was formed by four exceptional musicians and that the sound created spoke more strongly than the performing individuality of each one. In a trash band, the guitar is its sound spirit, followed by the vocals that need to be adequate and low enough to overpower the chords and drums.

At no point did I make reference to the double bass, which is played by Paulo Xisto Junior and, it should be noted that, in *Trash Metal*, this instrument is not really the protagonist; Not even the drums are and, if in the case of Sepultura this made history, it is because Igor is a phenomenal musician who, as his brother said, never took formal lessons to play. Andreas knew how to explore this characteristic along with the legacy of death and the musical ideas of Wagner Lamounier, who always valued fast and furious bass drums, seeking to overcome the common technique used for this instrument.

It is always an aberration when Brazilian journalism tries to place Sepultura within the national rock scene, claiming that it is the most international band that Brazil has in music. This is to diminish the guys and even belittle the fact that they are the biggest name in *Trash Metal* in the entire history of heavy music, with artistic and rhythmic creations and innovations for which specific study methods will still have to be created, with the possibility of not being able to understand what is being analyzed. The fact that three members of the band did not have formal music lessons allowed them to create and innovate in heavy music without the need to be tied to technical canons and, when Kisser joined, he interpreted it as an opportunity to create what he really wanted, as musician.

Sepultura is not considered the greatest ultra-heavy rock group in the history of music, because in its home country it is not recognized as such. Sepultura is Brazilian; But, it's not *from Brazil!* It does not represent the type of recognition that a group of fops and half-assed critics want for the Brazilian music scene. Even with all the merit achieved through their personal efforts, they are not seen as the *greatest Brazilian musical star*.

The only Brazilian TV channel that embraced the Caras' work, without modesty, was SBT, in the person of presenter Serginho Groisman, where on several occasions he presented the band playing live, participating freely with the audience of teenagers in which they responded to questions like these, without any embarrassment or editing cuts.

In the opposite direction, Rede Globo de Televisão, in 1994, made a point of presenting the group's lead singer to the Police Station in São Paulo, claiming that he had stepped on the National Flag. After clarifying the facts that he had not done any of this and that it was a fan club flag, they threw it onto the stage and he, together with his first son, Zyon, who was only 1 (one) year old at the time, took the flag and left for the dressing room.

The most brilliant, aggressive and fierce performance of Sepultura's career [*with their classic lineup*] took place on January 22, 1994, in the city of Rio de Janeiro, at the *Hollywood Rock 1994 event* . Angry and offended by the scam, they showed Brazil how real music is made, in an unforgettable show, in the Marvelous City.

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